
Code #1

Category: Benefits

Code: Team performance improvement

Coherent units: A10 - *"There was an increase in subjective performance and in the expert ratings of performance on a team level for all teams."*
A17 - *"The participants linked productivity with motivation in 20% of the positive feedback scenarios, indicating that these software engineers do not make the same connection as the literature that increased motivation increases productivity."*
G1 - *"This system not only maximizes productivity, but also minimizes turnover."*
G2 - *"Improve the performance of the remote team."*
G3 - *"It helps in determining the areas that require improvement."*
G10 - *"In fact, Cargill reports that feedback has increased performance by 40%—not only that, but 70% of their employees feel valued and have received helpful feedback."*
G15 - *"[Positive feedback] increases the engagement and future performance of your team."*
G18 - *"[Feedback] helps struggling employees grow and improve."*
G20 - *"The point of performance reviews, she says, is to 'give employees the opportunity to develop', which in turn helps the company grow."*

Code #2

Category: Benefits

Code: Increased individual engagement

Coherent units: G2 - *"Increase the employee's engagement."*
G10 - *"(...) it also helps encourage an attitude of continual learning and adjustment, and increases engagement."*
G13 - *"Improves morale and engagement within the team and organization as a whole."*
G14 - *"Effective positive feedback is an agent of engagement."*
G15 - *"[Positive feedback] increases the engagement and future performance of your team."*
G20 - *"The more we feel connected to the business, our leaders, and each other, the more productive and engaged we become."*

Code #3

Category: Benefits

Code: Better communication

Coherent units: G5 - *"Being open and allowing ourselves to be more vulnerable brought us much closer because we connected on a more personal level."*
G10 - *"By creating a space for team members to honestly and openly communicate about weaknesses in a workflow, problematic habits or behaviors, or other challenging topics, feedback nurtures better communication."*
G11 - *"Positive feedback is a great motivator and essential for building team spirit."*
G15 - *"Negative feedback (done well) can actually serve the same purpose. It does not have to be soul-sucking to you or your team; it's an opportunity to build resilience, improve as a group, and up-level each other."*
G16 - *"(...) establish trust, empathy and open lines of communication in the meantime."*

Code #4

Category: Benefits

Code: Increased individual motivation and job satisfaction

Coherent units: A1 - *“Process feedback has a positive effect on team members’ motivation and satisfaction for less motivated members.”*
A10 - *“Results imply that team process feedback has a positive effect on motivation, satisfaction, and performance in virtual teams.”*
A17 - *“Several motivation theories suggest that feedback is an important factor in motivation by providing information on performance or on the results of one’s actions”*
A21 - *“These quotations imply that feedback happens in the after-performance side of the work episode, so it can only influence job satisfaction.”*
G3 - *“Helps in motivating the team members.”*
G11 - *“It is one of the ways to keep people motivated.”*
G18 - *“[Feedbacks] are proven to increase job satisfaction and fulfillment.”*

Code #5

Category: Benefits

Code: Better alignment of the team members with the company’s objectives

Coherent units: G9 - *“Remote teams need these evaluations to keep everybody aligned with the company goals while being scattered all around the globe.”*
G14 - *“(…) More than 65% of employees felt fully connected with their work after receiving positive feedback from their leaders.”*
G20 - *“Rather, it is to strengthen your organization’s culture and reinforce its values.”*

Code #6

Category: Benefits

Code: Facilitation of business decision-making process

Coherent units: G10 - *“Feedback helps businesses to make wiser, more informed decisions about moving forward.”*
G11 - *“It is one of the ways to keep things moving in the right direction”*

Code #7

Category: Benefits

Code: Reduction of turnover rate

Coherent units: G1 - *“This system not only maximizes productivity but also minimizes turnover.”*
G4 - *“Providing employees with regular feedback helps avoid “blindsiding” them at formal evaluation time and reduces the stress that usually surrounds these reviews.”*
G14 - *“Companies that implement regular employee feedback see an average of 15% lower turnover rate.”*

Code #8

Category: Challenges

Code: Limited access to information

Coherent units: A11 - *“A virtual team member (and especially a distributed one who is isolated from other team members) has fewer mechanisms to gather information informally or to receive informal feedback and advice to realign goals and activities.”*
A13 - *“In virtual teams, feedback based on visual cues may be hard to interpret or nonexistent.”*
G1 - *“Too many managers and companies still rely on “time in the office” as a*

primary measure of evaluating performance. This has led to employees focusing more on “time logged on” rather than their actual contribution to the company.”

G2 - “In an office environment, managers can monitor the employees and their job performance in real-time. However, when it comes to remote working, things are not that easy, and keeping a tab on what employees are working on and what they’re struggling with is a complicated task.”

G18 - “You might not know all the little details of your remote engineer’s performance: after all, you haven’t been working side-by-side with them every day.”

G20 - “You don’t have as much data as you used to have because you’re no longer seeing your employees in person.”

Code #9

Category: Challenges

Code: Communication gap due to digital channels

Coherent units: A13 - “Communication in virtual teams has two challenges: sending information so that the message is heard and gathering feedback. (...) Seeking feedback presents another special communication challenge to virtual team members”
G7 - “Working across timezones makes it hard to have a dialogue.”
G8 - “One of the main differences is that supervisors and colleagues can no longer rely on general impressions gained from observing or collaborating with employees in person.”
G13 - “The fact that colleagues are isolated from one another, often communicating through chat, email, or video conferencing means there is higher potential to misinterpret intentions, avoid confrontation, or feel unheard and unappreciated.”
G14 - “It can be challenging for leaders to give feedback to remote workers since the interactions are limited.”
G15 - “The virtual experience erodes connection (...) Without body language and a physical presence, words have even more power.”
G17 - “The managers I interviewed also note that when they are giving feedback in person, they can adjust context to communicate the severity of the news. With his employees now working from home, he can’t control the setup that way.”

Code #10

Category: Challenges

Code: Raising negative emotions

Coherent units: A6 - “If personal anxiety to be replaced and an increased stress level, due to the COVID 19 crisis is neglected, valuable contributions and feedback from individuals are limited, resulting in hampered virtual team performance.”
G15 - “The daily news is negative (so) People need to feel grounded and confident at work.”
G17 - “Negativity bias can be a challenge in any feedback conversation, but it’s particularly problematic right now because of the chronic stress many people are experiencing as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. Research has shown that chronic stress is linked to a stronger negativity bias. You’re trying to help them get better, but they think you’re judging them, and harshly.”
G20 - “‘The psychological impact of Covid is hitting people in different ways’, he says.”

Code #11

Category: Challenges

Code: Maintaining a regular frequency of feedback delivery

Coherent units: G5 - “I had no idea how we were going to continue giving each other feedback virtually once we all returned home. As I predicted, we didn’t continue.”

G10 - *“Perhaps seeing feedback as “non-critical” or “non-essential,” they may communicate only out of urgency or absolute necessity.”*

G19 - *“Feedback is most powerful within 24 hours of when the circumstances occurred, so the recipient has clear recollection.”*

Code #12

Category: Challenges

Code: Delivering and receiving negative feedback

Coherent units: A16 - *“Feedback in some cases can actually be detrimental to performance, independent of whether the feedback itself is positive or negative. Feedback interventions can have unintended and potentially damaging effects on performance.”*

A17 - *“Positive feedback was found to have an impact on job satisfaction in 89% of all occurrences. Negative feedback had an impact on behavior in 73% of all occurrences.”*

G4 - *“For a remote employee, a poor performance evaluation can be discouraging and demotivating.”*

Code #13

Category: Challenges

Code: Lack of mechanisms to measure the individual’s evolution

Coherent units: A11 - *“A virtual team member (and especially a distributed one who is isolated from other team members) has fewer mechanisms to gather information informally or to receive informal feedback and advice to realign goals and activities.”*

G18 - *“You need to properly measure their performance and communicate it to them in a helpful way, all through virtual methods.”*

Code #14

Category: Recommendations

Code: Use of multidimensional indicators in the evaluation of team members

Coherent units: A13 - *“Use valid team performance measures as the bases for team recognition and reward. Careful development of team performance templates helps managers align virtual teams with strategic organizational objectives.”*

A15 - *“Recommends avoiding any feedback that might be construed as a normative comparison”*

G3 - *“Include the topics not covered in typical performance metrics.”*

G8 - *“Adapt performance measures as needed after a pivot to remote work. Remember that most are experiencing remote work for the first time.”*

G9 - *“First, create goals for the team. You have to make sure the goals you set are achievable (so you don’t set your team up to fail!) and aligned with the company goals (otherwise, it’ll be just a waste of time). To make sure you do that, you can use the SMART goal framework or the OKRs methodology. (...) Your team members must be aware of how and why their performance has to be evaluated. The clearer are your expectations and assignments, the better.”*

G18 - *“Understanding each employee is essential to providing them with good feedback down the road. Setting expectations throughout the employee’s journey with the business is also crucial.”*

G20 - *“Fully recognize the very different and varied circumstances in which team members are operating. With team members working from home, their approach calls for ‘A little more flexibility, a little more heart, and a little more leniency’”*

Code #15

Category: Recommendations

Code: Involve the entire team

Coherent units: A13 - *“Complement the performance templates with a 360-degree evaluation model to provide the developmental feedback for virtual teams and their members essential for continuous improvement.”*
G11 - *“Set up regular 360-degree feedback moments.”*
G16 - *“We encourage teams to share their working styles, including their feedback preferences, early on.”*

Code #16

Category: Recommendations

Code: Creation of a trusted environment

Coherent units: A1 - *“Managers should create and support conditions that foster a climate of intra-team trust. Encouraging initial face-to-face contact among team members and promoting the use of social networks can be useful strategies for that.”*
G6 - *“Take the first 10 - 15 minutes to talk about something fun, light-hearted, and more personal in the beginning. Since “building trust and rapport across the team” is the #1 thing remote managers should prioritize (33% of remote managers said this).”*
G13 - *“Create a space where everyone feels empowered to share their opinion.”*
G19 - *“Ask them to go further by asking them what they’d like to see instead. When you’re able to gather the context and a suggestion for now it could be better next time, that truly sets up the person receiving the feedback for success.”*

Code #17

Category: Recommendations

Code: Adoption of a template for feedback

Coherent units: G2 - *“Use a template.”*
G13 - *“Using templates like our retrospective, for example, provides structure and guides the process.”*
G16 - *“Give feedback in a more structured way.”*

Code #18

Category: Recommendations

Code: Adoption of two-way communication channels

Coherent units: A4 - *“Use two-way communications channels such as teleconferences so that the delivery of feedback can be followed immediately by an interactive problem solving or counseling session.”*
G2 - *“Be an active listener and focus on areas of improvement.”*
G9 - *“It’s important that this meeting be really a conversation. Let your employees, too, speak and ask them their input on how the work went and what things can be changed or improved.”*
G16 - *“The recipient and feedback-giver are aligned and able to wrap up the conversation with clarity.”*
G20 - *“Listen carefully and encourage forward and backward communication.”*

Code #19

Category: Recommendations

Code: Use of video calls

Coherent units: A3 - *“Since regular face-to-face interaction is not feasible, managers communicate with routine phone calls or e-mails to keep isolated team members in the loop.”*
G3 - *“You should try to do it through a video call rather than a phone call. The benefit of doing this is that you will be able to see the facial expression and body language of your employees.”*
G5 - *“Give feedback face-to-face (in a video call).”*
G13 - *“Ensure that there is time for one-on-ones, and leave your camera on.”*
G14 - *“I like to use Zoom for video calls. This gives a more personal touch to the relationship with employees. (...) Taking the time to smile, make eye contact, and speak in a friendly (but natural) tone can significantly improve the way remote workers receive and act upon your feedback.”*
G16 - *“Keeping your video on can help with the overall engagement of your audience. However, keeping the video on can become tiring over time, so I leave it up to my team’s preference.”*
G18 - *“Always use video calls. (...) can make both parts feel comfortable and help ensure that nothing is lost in communication.”*
G20 - *“‘For this kind of conversation, video is really important’, says Tavis. ‘It’s more personal and human.’ (...) Pay close attention to body language—both yours and that of your employees.”*

Code #20

Category: Recommendations

Code: Use a feedback-dedicated software tool

Coherent units: G7 - *“Combine with a thoughtful implementation of software to support ongoing feedback.”*
G8 - *“Adopt a modern software solution to facilitate remote performance management. Performance management software can assist you in tracking employee performance and equipping employees to progress in their careers.”*
G9 - *“Keep everybody on the same page by using a goal tracker software. Since you and your team cannot meet in person, you’ll need an online tool that’s easy for employees to access, and for managers to use for reporting.”*
G11 - *“Selecting the right tool, and particularly one that supports other areas of your performance strategy can help make the process even smoother.”*

Code #21

Category: Recommendations

Code: Feedback must be specific about the aspect under evaluation

Coherent units: A15 - *“Recommends providing feedback about how well the user is progressing toward the accomplishment of a specific task.”*
A16 - *“Focus on the task and task performance only, not on the person or any part of the person’s selfconcept.”*
G3 - *“Evaluate the performance of each member of the virtual team based on the quality of work they have delivered and whether they delivered it on time or not.”*
G4 - *“Providing meaningful and specific feedback.”*
G5 - *“Be specific, don’t generalise.”*
G8 - *“Focus on results rather than work processes. Rather than micromanaging employees and encouraging certain working styles, focus on the results that employees produce.”*
G12 - *“Focus on encouraging better performance in the future.”*
G14 - *“You should focus your critique on the task, skill, or project that needs to be improved.”*
G15 - *“Make it [feedback] more specific.”*
G17 - *“Be clear that they’re being evaluated on their results, not their effort”*

Code #22

Category: Recommendations

Code:	Keeping the feedback regular
Coherent units:	<p>A4 - <i>“Hold regularly scheduled virtual meetings with each team member.”</i></p> <p>G3 - <i>“Carry out performance reviews on a regular basis.”</i></p> <p>G4 - <i>“[Avoid] not providing feedback regularly.”</i></p> <p>G6 - <i>“Have lightweight, meaningful check-ins twice a year, combined with regular one-on-one meetings.”</i></p> <p>G7 - <i>“Training is crucial, alongside routines to put feedback at the heart of organizational culture.”</i></p> <p>G8 - <i>“Keep the lines of communication open with frequent feedback.”</i></p> <p>G10 - <i>“It may not be realistic to host regular, one-on-one video calls to gather feedback from individual team members, but you may want to host an occasional team check-in via Zoom or Skype.”</i></p> <p>G11 - <i>“Set up a standard time for 1-on-1s.”</i></p> <p>G13 - <i>“Ensure that there is time for one-on-ones”</i></p> <p>G14 - <i>“A PWC study revealed that 60% of employees would enjoy hearing feedback on a daily or weekly basis, with 72% of young employees particularly saying they’d enjoy more regular feedback.”</i></p> <p>G15 - <i>“Don’t wait for review time, or even the end of the week. (...) Give it early. (shortly after you start to notice a pattern of behavior).”</i></p> <p>G16 - <i>“It is important to communicate feedback regularly — once a month at a minimum. This provides our employees with a better understanding of how they are doing on a continuous basis.”</i></p> <p>G18 - <i>“Do it regularly.”</i></p> <p>G20 - <i>“You may need smaller, more frequent assessments, such as semi-annual or quarterly check-ins. This will give you, the manager, an opportunity to provide real feedback, and give employees a chance to make adjustments and calibrations.”</i></p>

Code #23

Category:	Recommendations
Code:	Clear feedback message
Coherent units:	<p>A15 - <i>“Feedback should be simple and clear.”</i></p> <p>G5 - <i>“Use simple language”</i></p> <p>G6 - <i>“Keep salary adjustments completely separate from the performance review and have it handled by HR.”</i></p> <p>G9 - <i>“Always remember to be constructive (...) all the parties involved must understand that the evaluation benefits the whole team.”</i></p> <p>G12 - <i>“Remember to give authentic feedback close to the action or behavior. If you’re delivering difficult feedback, allow the report enough time to assimilate it.”</i></p> <p>G17 - <i>“Clarify and contrast. (...) finds that contrasting statements can bring clarity. After you’ve raised your concern or suggestion, follow it with, “What I mean is X. What I don’t mean is Y.””</i></p>

Code #24

Category:	Recommendations
Code:	Provide feedback as simple as possible
Coherent units:	<p>A15 - <i>“Feedback should be simple and clear.”</i></p> <p>G3 - <i>“Create a performance assessment form and include all the important factors which affect the success of the project.”</i></p> <p>G4 - <i>“Balancing out the positives and negatives points.”</i></p> <p>G14 - <i>“Giving small pieces of advice frequently as opposed to delivering a lot of information at once.”</i></p> <p>G15 - <i>“Focus on facts without assuming intent.”</i></p>

Code #25

Category:	Recommendations
Code:	Make the feedback expectations clear
Coherent units:	G4 - <i>"Clear expectations for future work"</i> G5 - <i>"Focus on things that the person can actually change."</i> G6 - <i>"Actively clarify expectations."</i> G10 - <i>"Give guidelines in terms of meeting flow and expectations."</i> G12 - <i>"To improve your chances of driving the behavior you want from your report, you can close the feedback by asking about the report's intent."</i> G14 - <i>"Communicating your expectations and giving actionable advice gives remote workers the opportunity to learn from their failures."</i> G19 - <i>"Ensure you are clear on what each person is telling you – ask them to provide an example or a story to bring their words to life."</i> G20 - <i>"Provides employees with specific and useful information about what they did well and where they could improve"</i>

Code #26

Category:	Recommendations
Code:	Provide a goal-oriented development plan
Coherent units:	A16 - <i>"Include a formal goal-setting plan along with the feedback. (...) The inclusion of goal-setting increases the effectiveness of any feedback intervention."</i> G2 - <i>"Create an effective performance improvement plan based on the review."</i> G4 - <i>"Encouraging further growth and setting goals."</i> G5 - <i>"Offer mentoring"</i> G8 - <i>"Share development plans to help employees progress. Development plans guide employees in advancing their skills and preparing them for the next step in their careers."</i> G11 - <i>"Make sure to continue setting and tracking personal development goals as well as business ones."</i>

Code #27

Category:	Recommendations
Code:	Recognize an individual's good performance
Coherent units:	G2 - <i>"Do not just focus on employees who aren't performing as well as others. Instead, effectively communicate the feedback to your top performers and appreciate them for their excellent work."</i> G8 - <i>"Celebrate everyday accomplishments."</i> G11 - <i>"Make sure to give your remote team members positive feedback regularly and encourage peers to celebrate successes, even online."</i> G15 - <i>"Remind the employee of when they did well."</i> G20 - <i>"Be sure to take this opportunity to recognize and show appreciation for employees 'who are working hard, engaged, committed and offering their support to others.'"</i>

Code #28

Category:	Recommendations
Code:	Constant follow-up
Coherent units:	A1 - <i>"A period of reflection after providing feedback may improve the effectiveness of a feedback intervention."</i> A4 - <i>"Ensure rapid responses to electronic communications, reliable performance, and consistent follow-through. (...) Team leaders should communicate frequently with individual team members."</i>

A16 - *“A coach can help further motivate employees who receive positive feedback from various sources, while helping the recipients of negative feedback formulate a workable strategy for performance improvement”*

G5 - *“Remember that people need time to change.”*

G9 - *“Check all the metrics and see how they have progressed. By the end of it you should be able to answer these questions: Were the objectives reached? Why / why not? Were there issues (team-wide or otherwise)? Why / why not? Which metrics have been improved? Why? How?”*

G18 - *“Check in after the performance review.”*

Code #29

Category: Recommendations

Code: Constantly adjust the performance evaluation

Coherent units: G8 - *“Adapt performance measures as needed after a pivot to remote work. Remember that most are experiencing remote work for the first time.”*
G11 - *“Encourage regular check-ins and conduct engagement surveys.”*
